

Botanicals: The most suitable tool for Crop Health Management

Dr. S. Malarvannan

Associate Professor (Agricultural Entomology), School of Agriculture,
Bharath Institute of Higher Education and Research, Selaiyur, Chennai, India

Introduction

Globally, Agriculture is facing numerous challenges including climate change, biodiversity loss and rising demands for food production (Rockstrom *et al.*, 2009; Tilman *et al.*, 2011; Deutsch *et al.*, 2018). Pests and diseases destroy up to 40% of the world's food crops each year. This incurs an annual agricultural trade loss of more than \$220 billion, and results in hunger, and eventually interferes with rural income (Vandana and Uniyal, 2021). Pesticides are the cornerstones upon which the pest management practices are based, and are likely to remain so as long as effective and inexpensive chemicals are available (Haynes, 1988). It is estimated that more than 6,500 species of plants have been examined for anti-insect properties. Of these, more than 2,500 species belonging to 235 families have shown a bio pesticide activity (Celis *et al.*, 2008; Walia *et al.*, 2012). Plant as whole or extracts have been used as herbal drugs since ages.

Botanical Pesticides – A rich resource

Botanical pesticides are naturally occurring chemicals extracted from plants. Natural pesticidal products are available as an alternative to synthetic chemical formulations but they are not necessarily less toxic to humans. Some of the most deadly, fast acting toxins and potent carcinogens occur naturally (Regnault-Roger *et al.*, 2005; Regnault-Roger and Philogène, 2008). The characteristic features of the botanical pesticides such as lack of persistence and bioaccumulation in the environment, selectivity towards beneficial insects and low toxicity to humans (Grdisa and Grsic, 2013) led to the significant studies of botanical pesticides from different plant sources. They are generally safer to humans and the environment than conventional chemical pesticides (Dimetry, 2014). The terms “botanical insecticide”, “plant extracts”, biopesticides, “insecticidal activity” or “pesticidal activity” revealed 15 (33.3%) (Apiaceae, Apocynaceae, Asteraceae, Boraginaceae, Brassicaceae, Campanulaceae, Fabaceae, Lamiaceae, Myrtaceae, Papaveraceae, Polygonaceae, Primulaceae, Proteaceae, Rosaceae, Rubiaceae and

Scro- phulariaceae) out of 44 plant families that have been involved in habitat manipulation studies, had at least one plant genus or species with insecticidal activity. Pro- teaceae had one plant used in habitat manipulation in the same genus as another plant used as a biopesticide. All other plant families had at least one plant species tried for its insecticidal activity and tested in habitat manipulation studies (Fiedler *et al.*, 2008; Lavandero *et al.*, 2006; Vattala *et al.*, 2006).

Types of Botanicals Insecticides and their effects

Essential oils

Essential oils extracted from aromatic plants have increased considerably as insecticides owing to their popularity with organic growers and environmentally conscious consumers. They have repellent, insecticidal, antifeedants, growth inhibitors, oviposition inhibitors, ovicides, and growth-reducing effects on a variety of insects (Don-Perdo, 1996; Elzen and Hardee, 2003; Koshier and Sedy, 2001; Lu, 1995; Pereira *et al.*, 2006; Regnault-Roger *et al.*, 2012; Shelton *et al.*, 2002; Sithisut *et al.*, 2011; Tripathi *et al.*, 2003).

Alkaloids

Alkaloids are the most important group of natural substances playing an important role in insecticidal (Balandrin *et al.*, 1985; Rattan, 2010). Wachira *et al.*, (2014) concluded that pyridine alkaloids extracted from *Ricinus communis* against the malaria vector *Anopheles gambiae*. Furocoumarin and quinolone alkaloids extracted from *Ruta chalepensis* leaves showed larvicidal and antifeedant activities against the larvae *Spodoptera littoralis* (Emam *et al.*, 2009). Acheuk and Doumandji-Mitiche (2013) found that alkaloids extract of *Pergularia tomentosa* caused antifeeding and larvicidal effects. Lee (2000) concluded that piperonaline and piperidine alkaloids have mosquito larvicidal activity. Alkaloids from *Arachis hypogaea* extract have larvicidal activity against chikungunya and malarial vectors (Velu *et al.*, 2015).

Flavonoids

Flavonoids could be useful in a pest-management strategy. Flavonoids play an important role in the protection of plants against plant feeding insects' and herbivores (Acheuk and Doumandji-Mitiche, 2013). Both flavonoids and isoflavonoids protect the plant against insect pests by influencing their behavior, growth, and development (Simmonds, 2003; Simmonds and Stevenson, 2001). Rutin and quercetin-3-glucoside in *Pinus banksiana* inhibit the development and increase the mortality of *L. dispar* (Gould and Lister, 2006). Quercetin and rutin glycosides in peanuts caused increased mortality of the tobacco armyworm (*Spodoptera litura*) (Mallikarjuna *et al.*, 2004). In rice, three flavone glucosides inhibit digestion in insects and function as deterrent agents in *Nilaparvata lugens* and herbivores (Acheuk and Doumandji-Mitiche, 2013).

Glycosides

Cyanogenic glycosides are known as plant defense chemicals and found in cassava, bamboo, flax, and other plants. They are effective against stored-product insects as fumigants. Due to their insecticidal activity to insects, cyanohydrins can be used as an alternative fumigant and also as soil fumigants (Park and Coats, 2002). Dave and Lediwane (2012) found that anthraquinones isolated from *Cassia* species possess as antimalarial and insecticidal activity. Glycosides from *A. hypogaea* extract have larvicidal activity against chikungunya and malarial vectors (Velu *et al.*, 2015). Juvenogens have a potential application in insect pest control (Wimmer *et al.*, 2007).

Esters and Fatty acids

Fatty acids methyl esters were isolated from *Solanum lycocarpum* have larvicidal activity against the vector *C. quinquefasciatus* (Silva *et al.*, 2015). Mullens *et al.* (2009) showed that saturated fatty acids (particularly C8, C9 and C10) used as repellents or antifeedants against houseflies, horn flies and stable flies. Samuel *et al.* (2015) concluded that fatty acids mixture (C8910) has toxicity and repellence against insecticide susceptible and resistant strains of the major malaria vector *Anopheles funestus*. Yousef *et al.* (2013) reported that toxicity and reduction in larval body weight of linoleic acid against the larvae of *S. littoralis*.

Mode of Action of Botanicals

Botanical pesticides affect the insect pests in different ways depending on the physiological characteristics of the insect species as well as the type of the insecticidal plant. The components of various botanical insecticidal can be classified into six groups namely; repellents, feeding deterrents/ antifeedants, toxicants, growth retardants, chemosterilants, and attractants (Rajashekar *et al.*, 2012). Usually, the mode of action includes the specific enzyme, protein, or biological step affected. While most of the mode of action of the botanical pesticides are classified based on the pests controlled, physical characteristics, or chemical composition (Khambay *et al.*, 2003; Bloomquist *et al.*, 2008).

Repellents

A botanical pesticide have a repellent property, where keeps away the insect pest, and protect the crops (Isman, 2006) with minimal impact on the ecosystem, as they drive away the insect pest from the treated materials by stimulating olfactory or other receptors (Talukder, 2006; Talukder, *et al.*, 2004). Botanical pesticides are considered safe in pest control because they have low or none pesticide residue making them safe to the people, environment and ecosystem (Talukder *et al.*, 2004). Ghavami *et al.* (2017) found that essential oils of *Ziziphora tenuiore*, *Myrtus communis*, *Achillea wilhelmsii* and *M. piperita* have repellent activities against human fleas. Rahdari and Hamzei (2017) demonstrated the efficacy of *M. piperita*, *R. officinalis*, and

Coriandrum sativum oils for applying in organic food protection due to repellent activity of essential oils on *Tribolium confusum*.

Feeding deterrents/antifeedants

Botanical pesticides that inhibit feeding or disrupt insect feeding by rendering the treated materials unattractive or unpalatable (Rajashekar *et al.*, 2012; Talukder, 2006). The insects remain on the treated material indefinitely and eventually starve to death. Liao *et al.* (2017) demonstrated that oil of *M. alternifolia* and their chemical constituents possessed obvious antifeedant activities against *Helicoverpa armigera* Hubner. The phytoconstituents found in the leaf extract of *Khaya senegalensis* include tannins, saponins, flavonoids, steroids, and alkaloids may have been responsible for the mortality of *Dinoderus porcellus* (Loko *et al.*, 2017). Chaudhary *et al.*, (2017) and Ghoneim and Hamadah (2017) pointed that azadirachtin which is prominent constituent of neem established as a pivotal insecticidal ingredient. It acts as an antifeedant, repellent, and repugnant agent and induces sterility in insects by preventing oviposition and interrupting sperm production in males.

Growth retardants and development inhibitors

Botanical pesticides showed deleterious effects on the growth and development of insects, reducing the weight of larva, pupa and adult stages and lengthening the development stages (Talukder, 2006). Plant derivatives also reduce the survival rates of larvae and pupae as well as adult emergence (Koul *et al.*, 2008). It has been reported that both azadirachtin and neem seed oil increased aphid nymphal mortality significantly at 80 and 77%, respectively, and at the same time increasing development time of those surviving to adulthood (Kraiss and Cullen, 2008).

Neem based products

Neem based products are extracted from the neem tree, *Azadirachta indica*, a member of the Meliaceae family (Campos *et. al.*, 2016). The potent active ingredients of the neem are azadirachtin, meliantriol, salannin, desacetyl salannin, nimbin, desacetyl nimbin, and nimbidin. Azadirachtin, a tetranortriterpenoid limonoid, is one of the most potent active compounds of the neem tree (Mordue (Luntz) and Blackwell, 1993). Azadirachtin is present in higher concentration (0.2 – 0.6%) in the seeds of the neem compared to other parts of the neem tree (Govindchari, 1992). Azadirachtin A is the most active biological ingredient which shows insecticidal activity compared to other analogs of azadirachtin (Koul *et. al.*, 2004; Sola *et. al.*, 2014). Azadirachtin has a wide spectrum of actions on insects such as repellents, antifeedant, insect growth regulatory, and anti – ovipositional properties (Schmutterer, 1990; Bramhachari, 2004). It is most effective against 550 insect species, mostly relating to orders Dictyoptera, Orthoptera, Heteroptera, Isoptera, Lepidoptera, Diptera, Coleoptera, Homoptera, Siphonaptera and Hemiptera (Sadre *et. al.*, 1983; Mordue (Luntz) and Blackwell, 1993).

Pyrethrum

Pyrethrum is one of the most important botanical pesticides used in India, which is extracted from the flowers of *Chrysanthemum cinerariaefolium* (El-Wakeil, 2013). The higher concentration of pyrethrum is found mainly in the flowers of the plant compared to other parts of the plant (Rhoda *et. al.*, 2006; Isman, 2006; Sola *et. al.*, 2014). Pyrethrum is the mixture of six active ingredients, namely, pyrethrin I, pyrethrin II, cinerin I, cinerin II, jasmolin I, and jasmolin II. Pyrethrum, and Eucalyptus Leaf Extract has been registered and allowed to use as botanical pesticides commercially for various purposes under Insecticide Act, 1968. Out of three, Azadirachtin or neem based pesticides are mostly used as the botanical pesticides in the agricultural pest management system followed by pyrethrum, and Eucalyptus Leaf Extract.

Conclusion

Botanical pesticides from natural origin have greater scope in international as well as national level as they are comparatively safe, easily degradable and have multiple actions against insect pests. The source for the botanicals is also vast and there are many pesticidal plants which are yet to be explored. The increasing concern of the insect resistance to chemical pesticides has warranted the search for viable alternatives. The advantage of botanicals is the cost and it can be prepared by the farmers themselves without any sophisticated techniques. For a wider reach, many industries have come up with botanical formulations and are readily available in the market. The research findings prove that there is a steady and continuous increase in the preference for botanicals over the last 10 years. Hence, the future emphasis should be on development of a wide range of botanical formulations with the particular molecules for better performance. This will ensure sustainable agriculture and will enhance the beneficial insects, thus maintain a biotic balance. However, all the botanicals are not safe to human being, hence adequate precautionary measures has to be followed while spraying the botanical pesticides in the field. Plant-based pesticides are predominantly used in low-income and emerging nations to control pests because of their cost-effectiveness, availability, accessibility, and easy-to-use.

References

- Acheuk, F. and Doumandji-Mitiche, B. (2013). Insecticidal activity of alkaloids extract of *Pergularia tomentosa* (Asclepiadaceae) against fifth instar larvae of *Locusta migratoria cinerascens* (Fabricius 1781) (Orthoptera: Acrididae). *International Journal of Science and Advanced Technology*, 3(6), 8–13.
- Aerts, R.J. and Mordue, A.J. (1997). Feeding Deterrence and Toxicity of Neem Triterpenoids. *Journal of Chemical Ecology*, 23, 2117-2132.
- Arora, R, Singh, B. and Dhawan, A. K. (2012). *Theory and Practice of Integrated Pest Management*. Jodhpur: Scientific Publishers.

- Asawalam, E. and Adesiyun, S. (2001). Potential of *Ocimum basilicum* (Linn) for the control of maize weevil *Sitophilus zeamais* (Motsch). *Nigeria Agricultural Journal*, 32(1), 195–201.
- Asghar U, Malik, M.F. and Javed, A. (2016). Pesticide Exposure and Human Health: A Review. *J. Ecosys. Ecograph*, S5: 005. DOI: 10.4172/2157-7625.S5-005.
- Auger, J. and Thibout, E. (2002). Substances soufrées des Allium et des Crucifères et leurs potentialités phytosanitaires. In: Regnault-Roger C, Philogène BJR, Vincent C (Eds) *Biopesticides d'Origine Végétale*. Lavoisier Tech and Doc, Paris, pp 77–95.
- Balandrin, M. F, Klocke, J. A, Wurtele, E. S, and Bollinger, W. H. (1985). Natural plant chemicals: Sources of industrial and medicinal materials. *Science*, 7; 228(4704), 1154–1160. <https://doi.org/10.1126/science.3890182>.
- Batish D.R, Singh, H.P, Setia, N, Kaur, S. and Kohli, R.K. (2006). Chemical composition and phytotoxicity of volatile essential oils from intact and fallen leaves of *Eucalyptus citriodora*. *Z. Naturforsch.* c61: 465 – 471.
- Batish, D.R, Singh, H.P, Kohli, R.K. and Kaur, S. (2008). Eucalyptus essential oil as a natural pesticide. *For. Ecol. Manag.*, 256: 2166 – 2174.
- Belmain, S.R, Amoah, B.A, Nyirenda, S.P, Kamanula, J.F. and Stevenson, P.C. (2012). Highly Variable Insect Control Efficacy of *Tephrosia vogelii* Chemotypes. *Journal of Agricultural and Food Chemistry*, 60, 10055-10063. <http://dx.doi.org/10.1021/jf3032217>.
- Bloomquist, J.R, Boina, D.R, Chow, E, Carlier, P.R, Reina, M and GonzalezColoma, A. (2008). Mode of action of the plant-derived silphinenes on insect and mammalian GABAA receptor/chloride channel complex. *Pestici Biochem and Physiol* 91:17–23.
- Celis, Á, Mendoza, C, Pachón, M, Cardona, J, Delgado, W. and Cuca, L.E. 2008. Extractos vegetales utilizados como biocontroladores con énfasis en la familia Piperaceae. Una revisión. *Agron. Colomb.* 26(1), 97-106.
- Campos, EVR, de Oliveira, JL, Pascoli, M, de Lima R and Fraceto, L.F. (2016). Neem oil and crop protection: From now to the future, *Front Plant Sci.*, 7:1494.
- Chaudhary, S, Kanwar, R. K, Sehgal, A, Cahill, D. M, Barrow, C. J, Sehgal, R. and Kanwar, J. R. (2017). Progress on *Azadirachta indica* based biopesticides in replacing synthetic toxic pesticides. *Frontiers in Plant Science*, 8, 610.
- Dave, H. and Lediwane, L. (2012). A review on anthraquinones isolated from *Cassia* species and their applications. *Indian Journal of Natural Products and Resources*, 3, 291–319.
- Deutsch, C. A., Tewksbury, J. J., Tigchelaar, M., Battisti, D. S., Merrill, S. C., Huey, R. B., et al. (2018). Increase in crop losses to insect pests in a warming climate. *Science* 361, 916–919.
- Dimetry, N.Z. (2014). Different Plant Families as Bio resources for Pesticides. In: *Advances in Plant Biopesticides*, D. Singh (Ed.), Springer India. DOI: 10.1007/978-81-322-2006-0_1.
- Don-Perdo, K. M. (1996). Investigation of single and joint fumigant insecticidal action of citrus peel oil components. *Journal of Pest Science*, 46, 79–84.

- Elzen, G. W., and Hardee, D. D. (2003). United state department of agricultural-agricultural research on managing insect resistance to insecticides. *Pest Management Science*, 59, 770–776. <https://doi.org/10.1002/> (ISSN) 1526-4998.
- Emam, A. M, Swelam, E. S. and Megally, N. Y. (2009). Furocoumarin and quinolone alkaloid with larvicidal and antifeedant activities isolated from *Ruta chalepensis* leaves. *Journal of Natural Products*, 2, 10–22.
- Fiedler, AK, Landis, DA. and Wratten, S.D. (2008). Maximizing ecosystem services from conservation biological control: the role of habitat management. *Biol Control* 45:254–271.
- Ghavami, M. B, Poorastgoo, F, Taghiloo, B. and Mohammadi, J. (2017). Repellency effect of essential oils of some native plants and synthetic repellents against human flea, *Pulex irritans* (Siphonaptera: Pulicidae). *Journal of Arthropod Borne Diseases*, 11(1), 105–115.
- Ghoneim, K. and Hamadah, K. (2017). Antifeedant activity and detrimental effect of Nimbecidine (0.03% Azadirachtin) on the nutritional performance of Egyptian cotton leaf worm *Spodoptera littoralis* Boisd. (Noctuidae: Lepidoptera). *Bio Bulletin*, 31, 39–55.
- Gould, K. S. and Lister, C. (2006). Flavonoid functions in plants. In *Flavonoids: Chemistry, biochemistry, and applications* (pp. 397–443). Boca Raton, FL: CRC Press LLC.
- Govindchari, TR. (1992). Chemistry and biological investigation on *Azadirachta indica* (the neem tree). *Curr. Sci.*, 63: 117 – 122.
- Grdisa, M. and Grsic, K. (2013). Botanical Insecticides in Plant Protection. *Agriculturae Conspectus Scientificus*, 78 (2): 85 – 93.
- Haynes, KF. (1988). Sub lethal effects of neurotoxic insecticides on insect behaviour. *Ann Rev Entomol* 33:149–168.
- Henn, T. and Weinzierl, R. (1989). *Botanical Insecticides and Insecticidal Soaps*. University of Illinois at Urbana Champaign, College of Agriculture, Cooperative Extension Service.
- Henn T, Weinzierl R, Gray M. and Steffey, K. (1991). *Alternatives in insect management: field and forage crops*. Cooperative extension service, University of Illinois at Urbana-Champaign, Circ. 1307.
- Hollingworth, R, Ahammadsahib, K, Gadelhak, G. and McLaughlin, J. (1994). New inhibitors of complex I of the mitochondrial electron transport chain with activity as pesticides. *Biochemical Society Transactions*, 22(1), 230–240.
- Isman, MB. (2006). Botanical insecticides, deterrents, and repellents in modern agriculture and an increasingly regulated world. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.*, 51: 45 – 66.
- Khambay, B.P, Batty, D, Jewess, P.J, Bateman G.L. and Hollomon, D.W. (2003). Mode of action and pesticidal activity of the natural product dunnione and of some analogues. *Pest Manag Sci* 59:174–182.
- Khater, H.F. (2012). Prospects of Botanical Biopesticides in Insect Pest Management. *Pharmacologia*, 3, 641-656. <http://dx.doi.org/10.5567/pharmacologia.2012.641.656>.
- Koshier, E. L, and Sedy, K. A. (2001). Effect of plant volatiles on the feeding and oviposition of Thrips tabaci. In R. Marullo, and L. Kound (Eds.), *Thrips and Tospoviruses* (pp. 185–187). Australia: CSIRO.

- Koul, O, Waliyai, S. and Dhaliwal, G. S. (2008). Essential oils as green pesticides: Potential and constraints. *Biopesticides International*, 4(1), 63–84.
- Koul O, Singh G, Singh R, Singh J, Daniewski, WM. and Berlozecki, S. (2004). Bioefficacy and mode of action of some limonoids of salannin group from *Azadirachta indica* A. Juss and their role in a multicomponent system against lepidopteran larvae. *J. Biosci.*, 29: 409 – 416.
- Kraiss, H. and Cullen, E. M. (2008). Insect growth regulator effects of azadirachtin and neem oil on survivorship, development and fecundity of *Aphis glycines* (Homoptera: Aphididae) and its predator, *Harmonia axyridis* (Coleoptera: Coccinellidae). *Pest Management Science*, 64(6), 660–668.
- Lavandero, B, Wratten, S.D, Didham, R.K. and Gurr, G. (2006). Increasing floral diversity for selective enhancement of biological control agents: a double-edged sword? *Basic Appl Ecol.* 7:236–243.
- Lee, S. E. (2000). Mosquito larvicidal activity of piperonaline, a piperidine alkaloid derived from long pepper, *Piper longum*. *Journal of the American Mosquito Control Association*, 16(3), 245–247.
- Liao, M, Xiao, J. J, Zhou, L. J, Yao, X, Tang, F, Hua, R. M, Cao, H. Q. (2017). Chemical composition, insecticidal and biochemical effects of *Melaleuca alternifolia* essential oil on the *Helicoverpa armigera*. *Journal of Applied Entomology*, 2017, 1–8.
- Loko, L. Y, Alagbe, O, Dannon, E.A, Datinon, B, Orobisi, A, Thomas-Odjo, A. and Tamò, M. (2017). Repellent effect and insecticidal activities of *Bridelia ferruginea*, *Blighia sapida*, and *Khaya senegalensis* leaves powders and extracts against *Dinoderus porcellus* in infested dried yam chips. *Psyche*, 2017 Article ID 5468202, 18 pages.
- Lu, F. C. (1995). A review of the acceptable daily intakes of pesticides assessed by the world health organization. *Regulatory Toxicology and Pharmacology*, 21, 351–364.
- Mallikarjuna, N, Kranthi, K. R, Jadhav, D. R, Kranthi, S. and Chandra, S. (2004). Influence of foliar chemical compounds on the development of *Spodoptera litura* in interspecific derivatives of groundnut. *Journal of Applied Entomology*, 128, 321–328.
- Mordue (Luntz), A.J. and Blackwell, A. (1993). Azadirachtin: An Update. *J. of Insect Physiology*, 39, 903-924.
- Park, D. S. and Coats, J. R. (2002). Cyanogenic glycosides: Alternative insecticides? *The Korean Journal of Pesticide Science*, 6(2), 51–57.
- Pereira, S. G, Sanaveerappanavar, V. T. and Murthy, M. S. (2006). Geographical variation in the susceptibility of the diamond back moth *Plutella xylostella* L. to *Bacillus thuringiensis* products and acyl urea compounds. *Pest Management*, 15, 26–26.
- Rahdari, T. and Hamzei, M. (2017). Repellency effect of essential oils of *Mentha piperita*, *Rosmarinus officinalis* and *Coriandrum sativum* on *Tribolium confusum* duval (Coleoptera: Tenebrionidae). *Chemistry Research Journal*, 2(2), 107–112.
- Rajashekar, Y., Bakthavatsalam, N., and Shivanandappa, T. (2012). Botanicals as grain protectants. *Psyche*, 2012, 1–13.
- Rattan, R. S. (2010). Mechanism of action of insecticidal secondary metabolites of plant origin. *Crop Protection*, 29, 913–920.
- Regnault-Roger C, Philogène BJR (2008) Past and current prospects for the use of botanicals and plant allelochemicals in integrated pest management. *Pharmac Biol* 46:41–52.

- Regnault-Roger C, Philogène BJR, Vincent C (eds). (2005). Biopesticides of plant origin. Lavoisier, Paris, p 313.
- Regnault-Roger, C. and Philogène, B. J. R. (2008). Past and current prospects for the use of botanicals and plant allelochemicals in integrated pest management. *Pharmaceutical Biology*, 46, 41–52.
- Regnault-Roger, C, Vincent, C. and Arnason, J. T. (2012). Essential oils in insect control: Low-risk products in a high-stakes world. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 57, 405–424.
- Rhoda B, Freyer, B. and Macharia, J. (2006). Towards reducing synthetic pesticide imports in favour of locally available botanicals in Kenya. Conference on International Agricultural Research for Development. October 11 – 13, 2006, Tropentag, Bonn. Retrieved from <http://www.tropentag.de/2006/abstracts/full/158.pdf>.
- Rockstrom, J, Stefen, W, Noone, K, Persson, A, Chapin, F.S, Lambin, E, Lenton, T.M, Schefer M, Folke C, Schellnhuber HJ, Nykvist B, de Wit CA, Hughes T, van der Leeuw S, Rodhe H, Sorlin S, Snyder PK, Costanza R, Svedin U, Falkenmark M, Karlberg L, Corell RW, Fabry VJ, Hansen J, Walker B, Liverman D, Richardson K, Crutzen P, Foley J. (2009). Planetary boundaries: exploring the safe operating space for humanity. *Ecol Soc* 14:32.
- Sadre, N.L, Deshpande, V.Y, Mendulkar, K.N. and Nandal, D.H. (1983). Male *Azadirachta indica* in different species. Proc. 2nd Int. Neem Conf., Rauischholzhausen, pp 482.
- Samuel, M, Oliver, S. V, Wood, O. R, Coetzee, M. and Brooke, B. D. (2015). Evaluation of the toxicity and repellence of an organic fatty acids mixture (C8910) against insecticide susceptible and resistant strains of the major malaria vector *Anopheles funestus* Giles (Diptera: Culicidae). *Parasites and Vectors*, 8, 321.
- Shelton, A. M, Zhao, J. Z. and Roush, R. T. (2002). Economic, ecological, food safety and social consequences of the deployment of B-transgenic plants. *Annual Review of Entomology*, 47, 845–881.
- Schmutterer, H. (1990). Properties and potential of natural pesticides from the neem tree, *Azadirachta indica*. *Annu. Rev. Entomol.*, 35: 271 – 297.
- Silva, V. C. B, Ribeiro Neto, J. A, Alves, S. N. and Li, L. A. R. S. (2015). Larvicidal activity of oils, fatty acids, and methyl esters from ripe and unripe fruit of *Solanum lycocarpum* (Solanaceae) against the vector *Culex quinquefasciatus* (Diptera: Culicidae). *Revista da Sociedade Brasileira de Medicina Tropical*, 48(5), 610–613.
- Simmonds, M. S. (2003). Flavonoid–insect interactions: Recent advances in our knowledge. *Phytochemistry*, 64, 21–30.
- Simmonds, M. S. and Stevenson, P. C. (2001). Effects of isoflavonoids from cicer on larvae of *Helicoverpa armigera*. *Journal of Chemical Ecology*, 27, 965–977.
- Sithisut, D, Fields, P. G. and Chandrapathya, A. (2011). Contact toxicity, feeding reduction and repellency of essential oils from three plants from the ginger family (Zingiberaceae) and their major components against *Sitophilus zeamais* and *Tribolium castaneum*. *The Journal of Stored Products*, 104, 1445–1454.
- Talukder, F. A. (2006). Plant products as potential stored product insect management agents-A mini review. *Emirates Journal of Food and Agriculture*, 18(1), 17–32.
- Talukder, F, Islam, M, Hossain, M, Rahman, M. and Alam, M. (2004). Toxicity effects of botanicals and synthetic insecticides on *Tribolium castaneum* (Herbst) and *Rhyzopertha dominica* (F.). Bangladesh. *Journal of Environmental Sciences*, 10(2), 365–371.

- Thibout, E. and Auger, J. (1997). Composés soufrés des Allium et lutte contre les insectes. *Acta Bot Gallica* 144:419–426.
- Thibout E, Lecomte C. and Auger, J. (1986). Substances soufrées des Allium et insectes. *Acta Bot Gallica* 143:137–142.
- Tilman, D., Balzer, C., Hill, J. and Befort, B. L. (2011), ‘Global food demand and the sustainable intensification of agriculture’, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences of the United States of America*, 108(50): pp. 20260–64.
- Tripathi, A. K., Prajapati, V., Khanuja, S. P. S., and Kumar, S. (2003). Effect of d-limonene on three stored-product beetles. *Journal of Economic Entomology*, 96, 990–995. <https://doi.org/10.1093/jee/96.3.990>.
- Vandana, M. and V.P. Uniyal. 2021. Insect pest diversity of standing crops and traditional pest management in agricultural areas of the Mandakini Valley, Garhwal Himalaya, Uttarakhand, India. *International journal of Horticulture, Agriculture and Food Science (IJHAF)* ISSN: 2456-8635 [Vol-5, Issue-4, Jul-Aug, 2021].
- Vattala, H.D, Wratten, S.D, Phillips, C.B. and Wackers, F.L. (2006). The influence of fewer morphology and nectar quality on the longevity of a parasitoid biological control agent. *Biol Cont* 39:179–185.
- Velu, K, Elumalai, D, Hemalatha, P, Babu, M, Janaki, A. and Kaleena, P. K. (2015). Phytochemical screening and larvicidal activity of peel extracts of *Arachis hypogaea* against chikungunya and malarial vectors. *International Journal of Mosquito Research*, 2(1), 01–08.
- Wachira, S. W, Omar, S, Jacob, J. W, Wahome, M, Alborn, H. T, Spring, D. R. and Torto, B. (2014). Toxicity of six plant extracts and two pyridine alkaloids from *Ricinus communis* against the malaria vector *Anopheles gambiae*. *Parasites and Vectors*, 7, 312.
- Walia, S, Kumar, D. and O. Koual. (2012). Botanical biopesticides in pest management: Potential and constraints. pp. 146-182. In: Koul, O., G.S. Dhaliwal, S. Khokhar, and S. Ram (Eds.). *Biopesticides in environment and food security: issues and strategies*. Scientific Publishers, Jodhpur, India.
- Weinzierl, R.A. (2000). Botanical insecticides, soaps, and oils. In: *Biological and Biotechnological Control of Insect Pests*, Ed. J. E. Rechcigl, N. A. Rechcigl, pp 101 – 121.
- Wimmer, Z, Alexandra, J. F. D. M, Floro, Zarevúcka, M, Wimmerová, M, Sello, G. and Orsini, F. (2007). Insect pest control agents: Novel chiral butanoate esters (juvenogens). *Bioorganic and Medicinal Chemistry*, 15(18), 6037–6042.
- Yousef, H., EL-Lakwah, S. F., & EL Sayed, Y. A. (2013). Insecticidal activity of linoleic acid against *Spodoptera littoralis* (BOISD.). *Egyptian Journal of Agricultural Research*, 91(2), 573.
- Zhang, W., Zhang, Z., Chen, Z., Liang, J., Geng, Z., Guo, S., Deng, Z. (2017). Chemical composition of essential oils from six *Zanthoxylum* species and their Repellent activities against two stored-product insects. *Journal of Chemistry*, Article ID 1287362, 7 pages.